

Apparent Density Evaluation Methods to Assess the Effectiveness of Soil Conditioning

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Abstract

A study was performed on the University Link and Northgate Link projects in Seattle, WA, to investigate the use of apparent density evaluation methods for the identification of air pockets and plugging issues in the chamber of EPB TBMs. Both air pockets and plugging issues can result from improper soil conditioning and the TBM's inability to mix the soil properly with the conditioning agents. An apparent density below unity indicates the formation of an air pocket in the top part of the chamber and an apparent density above the virgin soil density points to developing plugging issues in the cutterhead bays and pressurized chamber. From the conducted study it can be concluded that the presented apparent density evaluation methods are an effective way to identify issues in the excavation chamber of an EPB TBM and can be used as a mean to improve the soil conditioning process.

Keywords: EPB; soil conditioning; apparent density.

List of Symbols

Symbol	Unit	Description
∇	kN/m ³	Vertical chamber pressure gradient
<i>FIR</i>	%	Foam injection ratio
F_T	kN	Thrust force
<i>g</i>	m/s ²	Gravitational acceleration
<i>K</i>	-	Coefficient of lateral earth pressure
<i>L</i>	m	Length of excavation chamber
ρ	kPa	Pressure; horizontal bulkhead pressure
ρ_1	kPa	Pressure measured by chamber pressure sensor #1
ρ_{16}	kPa	Average of ρ_1 and ρ_6
ρ_2	kPa	Pressure measured by chamber pressure sensor #2
ρ_3	kPa	Pressure measured by chamber pressure sensor #3
ρ_4	kPa	Pressure measured by chamber pressure sensor #4
ρ_5	kPa	Pressure measured by chamber pressure sensor #5
ρ_6	kPa	Pressure measured by chamber pressure sensor #6
$\rho_{ambient}$	kPa	Ambient pressure of surrounding ground
<i>T</i>	kN-m	Cutterhead torque
<i>u</i>	kPa	Pore pressure
<i>v</i>	mm/min	Advance rate
<i>z</i>	m	Vertical distance; elevation

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z_B	m	Vertical distance between bottom two chamber pressure levels
z_T	m	Vertical distance between top two chamber pressure levels
γ	kN/m ³	Total unit weight of material in chamber
γ'	kN/m ³	Buoyant unit weight of the chamber soil
γ_f	kN/m ³	Unit weight of chamber fluid
ρ	g/cm ³	Total muck density; total density of material in chamber
ρ_f	g/cm ³	Density of chamber fluid
ρ_s	g/cm ³	Density of in-situ soil
ρ_w	g/cm ³	Density of water
ϱ	g/cm ³	Apparent density
ϱ_B	g/cm ³	Bottom chamber apparent density
ϱ_T	g/cm ³	Top chamber apparent density
σ_x	kPa	Horizontal stress in tunneling direction
σ_x'	kPa	Effective horizontal stress in tunneling direction
σ_z'	kPa	Effective vertical stress
τ_a	kPa	Yield stress of muck

*1 bar = 100 kPa

1 Introduction

Proper soil conditioning in EPB tunneling offers many advantages to the quality and productivity of the project. There are few operational parameters that can be used to clearly assess the soil conditioning performance such as advance rate, torque, thrust, chamber pressures, etc. One of the other parameters that potentially can be used is the apparent density. The apparent density of the material in the chamber was introduced by Guglielmetti et al. (2003) as the vertical chamber pressure gradient calculated from the physical relation between the horizontally measured excavation chamber pressures and the vertical distance between the pressure sensors. Guglielmetti et al. (2003) introduced apparent density as a measure to ensure the excavation chamber is filled with material. To guarantee face stability, the authors suggest to keep the apparent density over a certain limit so the material is able to transfer effective stress to the virgin soil, and thus provide support of the excavation face. This method was implemented in the Metro project in Porto, Portugal.

Bezuijen et al. (2005) compared the vertical gradient of the horizontal bulkhead pressures to the total density of excavation chamber material and discovered that the gradient is not necessarily representative of the muck total density. The authors assumed that the yield stress of the muck as well as the adhesion between the muck and the cutterhead and bulkhead material have an influence on the vertical gradient. They simplified the resulting pressure gradient to Equation (1).

$$\frac{dp}{dz} = \rho g \pm 2 \frac{\tau_a}{L} \quad (1)$$

Where $\frac{dp}{dz}$ is the vertical pressure gradient, p is the horizontal bulkhead pressure, z is the elevation, ρ is the total muck density, g is the gravitational acceleration, τ_a is the yield stress of the muck, and L is the length of the excavation chamber. In this equation, term $2 \frac{\tau_a}{L}$ is added or subtracted depending on the direction of the muck flow in the chamber.

Alavi Gharahbagh et al. (2013) suggest that if muck contains an excessive amount of foam, the excessive foam will travel to the top of the chamber and an air pocket will form. This pressurized foam pocket is able to counteract the face pressure temporarily until the released air dissipates into the surrounding ground. This is a bigger problem during mining stops, where foam is not constantly added compared to the mining cycles. Possible issues that can arise from the formation of such an air pocket are: support pressure drops, water and muck flow into chamber, overexcavation, surface settlements, and blowouts through screw conveyor and to surface. The authors used apparent density to identify the existence of an air pocket in the excavation chamber of the University Link Light Rail Tunnel project in Seattle, WA. They suggest that an apparent density below the density of water indicates an air pocket in the chamber. Alavi Gharahbagh et al. used a port through the top of the bulkhead and a ball valve to bleed the accumulated air from the chamber. Another method that was suggested by the authors was to reduce the amount of injected foam into the chamber by modifying the foam injection and expansion ratios.

Bezuijen and Talmon (2014) compared the vertical gradient of pressures measured on the front and backside of the cutterhead to the gradient of pressures measured on the bulkhead of the Botlek Railway EPB TBM. They found that the vertical gradient of the horizontally measured pressures increases slightly from the front to the back of the cutterhead and increases significantly from the cutterhead to the bulkhead. The gradients also fluctuate over time and can reach levels higher than the in-situ soil density, which indicates the presence of effective stress. The gradient of pressures measured on the bulkhead is higher in the bottom of the chamber than at the top, which indicates a separation of the muck in the chamber.

Maidl and Stascheit (2014) integrated active density control of muck in the excavation chamber in their process control software for mechanized tunneling. The authors determine the density of the material in the chamber from the advance rate, the volume of conditioning agents injected, and the quantity of material leaving the screw conveyor. The goal is an optimal consistency of the muck and a reduction of soil conditioner usage.

Mosavat and Mooney (2015) examined the vertical gradient of horizontally measured chamber pressure (at six elevations on the chamber bulkhead) for a 17.5 m diameter EPB TBM during the early portion of a tunneling project in Seattle. The average or global vertical chamber pressure gradient was found to be 10-20% less than the total density (unit weight) of the samples taken from the belt conveyor during tunneling through the cohesive clay/silt and till deposits. They also show that the gradient varied locally within the chamber. The local gradient near the top of the chamber was consistently smaller in magnitude than the gradient near the bottom of the chamber. Mosavat and Mooney (2015) proposed that the vertical gradient of horizontal chamber pressure measurements is a function of both density and the coefficient of lateral earth pressure in the excavation chamber (derivation presented in Section 2.1). They speculate that the underestimation of total muck density using the gradient suggests that the lateral earth pressure coefficient in the excavation chamber is less than unity. The vertical chamber pressure gradient was found to be similar in magnitude to the density of conveyor belt samples during tunneling through predominantly granular soils, suggesting the lateral earth pressure coefficient equals unity and the gradient serves as a measure of muck unit weight. Like Bezuijen (2005), Mosavat and Mooney (2015) presented data to illustrate differences in chamber pressure magnitude and gradient depending on whether muck was flowing upward or downward. They were not able to rationalize the difference.

Dobashi et al. (2007) and Dobashi et al. (2013) introduced and discussed a system for visualizing the muck flow inside the excavation chamber of an EPB TBM that was used on the SJ51 and SJ53 sections of the Metropolitan Expressway Central Circular Shinkjuku Route. Four flappers were installed in the excavation chamber of the EPB TBM and were rotated during the excavation. A relationship between flapper torque and muck flow velocity and deformation rate in the excavation chamber was established via numerical analysis. Muck flow velocity and deformation rate are indicators for the condition of muck in the excavation chamber (e.g., a high flow velocity but low deformation rate indicates clogging). Dobashi et al. (2007) used the measured flapper torque to identify regions of poor plastic muck flow and adjusted the injected additive volume in these regions to improve the muck flow.

This paper presents apparent density evaluation methods to assess the effectiveness of soil conditioning. In this context the term apparent density is defined as the vertical gradient of the horizontally measured chamber pressures divided by the gravitational acceleration. However, as shown in previous research summarized above, the apparent density is not necessarily equal to the actual density of the material in the chamber. Several factors can influence the relationship between apparent and actual density and a theoretical relationship can be formulated which will be discussed in more details in section 2.1.

2 Background

The theoretical relationship between the apparent density and the chamber pressures can be established by taking the muck density in the excavation chamber as well as the coefficient of lateral earth pressure into account (see Section 2.1). However, the apparent density is not only influenced by these factors but also by soil conditioning and operational parameters as described in Section 2.2.

2.1 Relationship between Apparent Density and Chamber Pressure Gradient

Mosavat and Mooney (2015) proposed that the vertical chamber pressure gradient is a function of total muck and fluid unit weights as well as the coefficient of lateral earth pressure. The horizontal pressure p ($p = \sigma_x$ where x is oriented in the direction of tunneling) measured by the chamber pressure sensors is theoretically a total pressure composed of pore fluid pressure u and lateral effective earth pressure σ'_x as shown in Equation (2). The vertical effective stress σ'_z is related to the horizontal effective stress σ'_x through the coefficient of lateral earth pressure K (Equation 3). Assuming that the soil pores are filled with a mixture of water and air and that the matric suction is negligible, u reflects both pore air and water pressure.

$$p = \sigma_x = \sigma'_x + u \quad (2)$$

$$p = \sigma_x = K\sigma'_z + u \quad (3)$$

Equation (4) shows the derivation of the vertical chamber pressure gradient ∇ . In this equation, K is the coefficient of lateral earth pressure, γ_f is the unit weight of the chamber fluid (weighted average of air and water), γ' is the buoyant unit weight of the chamber soil, and γ is the total unit weight of the chamber soil. Assuming K is constant with depth, the vertical chamber pressure gradient is the sum of $K\gamma'$ and γ_f . Equation (5) displays the relationship between the apparent density ρ , the term used in this paper, and the vertical chamber pressure gradient. g is the gravitational acceleration, ρ is the total density of the material in the chamber, and ρ_f is the density of the chamber fluid.

$$\nabla = \frac{d\sigma_x}{dz} = K \frac{d\sigma'_z}{dz} + \frac{du}{dz} = K\gamma' + \gamma_f = K(\gamma - \gamma_f) + \gamma_f = K\gamma + \gamma_f(1 - K) \quad (4)$$

$$\rho = \frac{\nabla}{g} = \frac{1}{g} \frac{d\sigma_x}{dz} = K\rho + \rho_f(1 - K) \quad (5)$$

The unit weights, the densities, and the coefficient of lateral earth pressure are unknown. There is no literature on the topic of K for conditioned soil in the chamber of an EPB TBM. If the excavated material inside the chamber is well-conditioned with negligible effective stress and shear stress, then $K = 1$ is a reasonable assumption. In this case, the apparent density ρ equals the actual density ρ of the chamber material.

2.2 Effects of Soil Conditioning and Operational Parameters on Apparent Density

Soil conditioners like foam and bentonite slurry are used in EPB tunneling to improve the excavated soil's behavior. Soil conditioners in general are used to:

- Decrease the soil's permeability,
- Decrease soil and soil/metal friction, and, therefore,
- Increase the soil's flowability and
- Reduce the torque and thrust

Injection of foam and liquid additives normally reduces the density of the material by increasing the soil's porosity through introducing low density material. Foam, consisting of around 90% air, has a very low density and when homogeneously mixed with the excavated soil (increasing the porosity) reduces the soil's density. Additives like bentonite also have a lower density than the excavated soil and can also reduce the density of the mix when homogeneously mixed with the excavated material.

Formation of Air Pocket. In general, foam is entrained within the soil in the form of small bubbles dispersed throughout the mass of the soil. If the soil is oversaturated with air bubbles or if proper mixing does not happen in the excavation chamber, some foam may not be entrained in the soil and instead will percolate to the top of the excavation chamber. The excess accumulation of foam can create an air pocket with a density below unity at the top of the excavation chamber. This pressurized pocket will support the face in a similar manner to traditional compressed air tunneling as a means of ground support. However, the pressurized air, having negligible viscosity, can escape into the surrounding soil or through leaks in the TBM or along the shield. During the TBM advance, this may not be a serious problem since the foam is continuously injected through the cutterhead. However, during periods between advances, such as ring-build or downtime between shifts, weekends or holidays, the escaping air can result in a reduction in the excavation chamber pressure to levels below those adequate to support the face.

The formation of an air pocket at the top of the TBM excavation chamber can lead to several issues most notably chamber pressure drops when tunneling is paused for extended periods between advances. This might lead to inadequate face support and possibility of water and material flowing into the chamber. Some of the risks posed by precipitous drops in face support are: misinterpretation of ambient soil and water pressures which can lead to over excavation, possibility of surface settlement, potential blowouts through the screw and to the surface, and an increase in the chance of methane explosion by providing compressed air rich in oxygen into the mix (Copur et al. 2012).

Formation of Soil Plug. Soil conditioners transform the soil into a flowable paste with lower friction by decreasing the soil's density and lubricating the soil particles. In addition, this reduces adhesion to parts of the TBM such as cutting tools, chamber walls, and screw conveyor. Without proper soil conditioning, soil flowability will decrease (compared to well-conditioned soil) due to an increase in friction. The excavated soil will adhere to the surfaces of the TBM, accumulate, compact, and finally plug openings in the cutterhead and screw conveyors depending on soil type and virgin soil behavior. This paper defines plugging as the process in which soil gets adhered to the cutterhead, excavation chamber, and screw conveyor structures. Compacted soil plugs the cutterhead openings and adheres to the back and front of the cutterhead. This plug usually rotates with the cutterhead. Compacted soil sticks to the bulkhead and the sides of the excavation chamber and usually stays in place unless a mixing bar is able to detach it from the structure. Compacted soil has a higher density than conditioned soil. Compacted soil will likely also transfer a higher pressure from the material weight to the bulkhead and contain structure so that the coefficient of lateral earth pressure is not unity. The effect on the apparent density is heightened when one pressure level is in an air pocket (top of the chamber) and the other is in compacted soil (bottom of the chamber). Plugging and an air pocket can go hand-in-hand when the escaped foam building the air pocket on top of the excavation chamber leaves the soil on the bottom without proper conditioning. Especially in soils with higher clay content and/or without initial lubrication by ground water, plugging is a substantial issue.

Influence of Operational Parameters. Operational parameters like torque, thrust, cutterhead rotation, and advance rate have an influence on the apparent density of the material in the excavation chamber and vice versa. Due to the rotation of the cutterhead there is a rotational friction force between the muck and the backside of the cutterhead and the backside of the excavation chamber. The magnitude of this force is dependent on the viscosity of the muck, rotational speed of cutterhead, torque, and thrust force. This force can decrease and/or increase the apparent density, depending on the location of the soil in the chamber during excavation. Unevenly applied thrust force also influences the distribution of apparent density in the excavation chamber. The advance rate of the TBM and the screw conveyor speed which define the amount of soil entering and exiting the excavation chamber also have an influence on the apparent density of the soil. During standstill, the operational parameters have no longer an effect on the apparent density. The soil's density increases in the chamber over time due to consolidation and migration of foam bubbles into the formation. However, if the foam bubbles migrate towards the top of the chamber, the soil's density in the top part of the chamber decreases.

3 Apparent Density Evaluation Methods

Two different methods have been used to evaluate the apparent density of the U230 and N125 tunneling projects. In both methods, the apparent densities in the chamber are compared to theoretical densities. As explained in section 2.1, the apparent density is not necessarily equal to the actual material density in the chamber due to a possible divergence of the earth pressure coefficient from unity. Therefore, the presented methods in this section take additional factors into account to assure the assumptions made (e.g., air pocket present) are valid.

In the first method, the apparent density is compared to the density of water, 1 g/cm^3 . If the excavation chamber is filled with water the apparent density would be 1 g/cm^3 . It can be assumed that if the apparent density drops below 1 g/cm^3 the chamber is filled with a lighter material than water. Furthermore, it can be assumed that this material is the foam that escaped from the soil's pores (no

other material in the process is lighter than water).

The second method compares the apparent density to the virgin soil density. If the excavation chamber is filled with conditioned soil, the density should be below the virgin soil density because the soil's density decreases due to bulking during excavation and decreases further with the addition of soil conditioners. If the apparent density is close to or above the virgin soil density, even though soil conditioners were injected, the soil has compacted and a plugging issue might have developed inside the chamber and/or within the cutterhead openings.

3.1 Apparent Density below Unity

An apparent density below unity is normally noticed in the top part of the excavation chamber when an air pocket is present. The accumulated air from the chamber can be released through controlled opening of a valve on the bulkhead of the chamber while mining. The valve used to bleed the air should be installed on the top part of the bulkhead where the air pocket normally accumulates. The air should only be bled while mining so the pressurized air can be replaced by the excavated soil without noticeable drop in EPB mining pressure. During the air bleeding process, the apparent densities as well as the pressures in the chamber should be monitored closely. If air is present in the chamber the apparent density in the top part of the chamber should increase while the valve is opened. This happens because the pressurized air in the top part of the chamber is replaced by soil. The pressures in the chamber will decrease when the valve is open since air pressure is released, which also allows the soil in the bottom part of the chamber to expand decreasing its apparent density. If this operation is performed properly, mining pressures should not drop below ambient. Only the observation of this behavior of apparent densities and pressures while the valve is open can prove that an air pocket was present. Since the air release process has to be performed during the mining process and as a result the operational parameters influence the apparent density, it is important to compare the apparent density values during the stops before and after the ring build cycle during which the air was released.

The TBM used on the U230 project was equipped with a manually operated air relief. The valve was upgraded to a hydraulically activated valve controlled by the TBM operator for the N125 project. A camera was installed to monitor the air bleeding process from the operator's cabin in the TBM and from the field engineer's office, Figure 1. It is important to open the valve and release the air in a controlled manner to avoid ground loss. Watching the process over camera helps to close the valve before other material like water or excavated material can exit the bulkhead through the port. The valve should also only be opened for very short periods at a time for the same reason. The opening and closing of the valve is a recorded parameter in the N125 data collection and management system and can later be used to analyze the data. The environment where the exhaust air from the chamber is released should be monitored closely by gas meters and ventilated properly.

3.2 Apparent Density above Virgin Soil Density

An apparent density above the virgin soil density is normally noticed in the bottom part of the excavation chamber when the soil accumulates and plugs the cutterhead openings. Plugging of the cutterhead decreases the advance rate and increases thrust and torque in addition to the noticeable apparent density change. Only the simultaneous observation of high apparent density, decreasing advance rate, and increasing thrust and torque without other possible reasons can prove that a plug has developed. In addition, the plug can increase the temperature of muck and machine parts, which should also be monitored. The plugging can be resolved by adjusting the soil conditioning regimen. The foam injection ratio can be increased and a dispersing agent can be added to the foam solution. However, the plugging can only be resolved in early stages and progresses very fast to levels where it cannot be resolved by a change in soil conditioning. A cutterhead intervention might be necessary for advanced stages of plugging. It is, therefore, advised to monitor the development of apparent density and operational parameters closely to be able to react in a timely manner.

In section 4, a brief summary of the Northgate Link (N125) and University Link (U230) projects and the geotechnical description of each of these two projects is presented prior to moving to section 5 and analysis of data.

4 U230 and N125 Projects

The University Link project is a 5.1 km light rail extension that runs in twin-bored tunnels from Downtown Seattle to the University of Washington, with stations at Capitol Hill and on the University of Washington campus near Husky Stadium. The project is broken up into two major excavation contracts, U220 that excavated the University of Washington Station (UWS) and the 3.45 km of twin-bored tunnels between UWS and the Capitol Hill Station (CHS) and U230 that excavated the CHS and the 1.2 km of twin-bored tunnels from the CHS to the Pine Street stub tunnel (PSST) in Downtown Seattle. The tunnels

Figure 1. Air pocket relief valve as seen through the camera (left) and schematic of the air relief valve (right)

for both U220 and U230 are lined with precast concrete segments having an outside diameter of 6.3 m and an inside diameter of 5.7 m.

The Seattle area has a complicated geologic history. Six major glacial events have happened during last 2 million years with intervening non-glacial erosional and depositional periods. The geological description of the U230 project can be divided into fluvial deposits, glacial deposits, lacustrine and glaciolacustrine deposits, all of which have been glacially over-ridden and are therefore highly overconsolidated. The geologic units of the U230 project, shown in Figure 2, include Fill (brown), Till and Till-like Soil (light pink), Till-like Soil (dark orange), Outwash (plum), Fluvial Sand (yellow), Lacustrine Sand (orange), Silt (light and dark turquoise), Clay (light and dark purple), and Organic Material (green).

The Northgate Link Extension will extend light rail service in Seattle north from the University of Washington to the University District, Roosevelt, and Northgate neighborhoods by 2021, and is expected to cost approximately \$2.1 Billion. Most of this 6.9 km extension will be underground, and the N125 contract includes the construction of 5.6 km of twin earth pressure balanced (EPB) tunnels. Also included are the excavation of the Maple Leaf Portal (MLP) where the light rail will transition from tunnels to elevated guide-way and two large underground station boxes, one for the University District Station (UDS) and one for the Roosevelt Station (RVS). The first part of the project connects MLP and RVS, the second part connects RVS and UDS, and the third part connects UDS and UWS. The tunnels are approximately 6.44 m in diameter and are to be furnished with concrete segmental tunnel lining having an outside diameter of 6.3 m and an inside diameter of 5.7 m.

The geologic description of the N125 project can be divided into glacial and non-glacial sediments of the Puget Trough deposited during the Quaternary and Holocene periods. The Quaternary sediments are generally overconsolidated due to several glaciations, while the recent Holocene sediments are normally consolidated. The Engineering Soil Units (ESU) defined for this project are Engineering and Non-

Figure 2. Subsurface geology of the U230 tunnel alignment between CHS and PSST (Irish 2009). Soil Units are Fill (brown), Till and Till-like Soil (light pink), Till-like Soil (dark orange), Outwash (plum), Fluvial Sand (yellow), Lacustrine Sand (orange), Silt (light and dark turquoise), Clay (light and dark purple), Organic Material (green)

Engineered Fill (ENF, white), Recent Granular Deposits (RGD, yellow), Recent Clays and Silts (RCS, grey), Till and Till-Like Deposits (TLD, purple), Cohesionless Sand and Gravel (CSG, orange), Cohesionless Silt and Fine Sand (CSF, green), and Cohesive Clay and Silt (CCS, blue), Figure 3. ENF, RGD, and RCS are recent, normally consolidated sediments, whereas TLD, CSG, CSF, and CCS are glacial, overconsolidated sediments. The clogging potential of CCS and TLD has been evaluated with the approach presented by Thewes and Burger (2004) and was baselined as medium to high.

Based on the geotechnical baseline report (GBR, Soundtransit 2013), the groundwater pressures at the tunnel invert of the N125 tunnels can reach up to 2.9 bar (29 m of waterhead). Groundwater pressure ranges between 0.1 to 2 bar from MLP to RVS, 0.8 and 2.6 bar from RVS to UDS, and 0.8 and 2.9 bar from UDS and UWS. In parts of the alignment the tunnel cross-sections will be partially and in some locations completely above the groundwater level. Below the groundwater level CSG and TLD soil units are expected to be saturated while CCS and CSF soil units are expected to contain lenses of saturated silt and sand that are hydraulically connected to other water-bearing soils. Silt and sand layers or lenses within fine-grained ESUs like RCS, TLD, CSF, and CCS can also contain perched groundwater.

The same EPB tunnel boring machine (TBM) was used for the excavation of both tunnels of the U230 project, subsequently referred to as TBM #1. The alignments of the two U230 tunnels run parallel with only a short distance between the northbound (NB) and southbound (SB) tunnels. The soil conditioning program was slightly adjusted after the excavation of the first tunnel (NB). TBM #1 was also used for the excavation of the N125 NB tunnel after being refurbished, and a second EPB TBM from a different

Figure 3. Subsurface geology of the N125 tunnel alignment from MLP (top right) to UWS (bottom left). ESUs shown are white ENF, yellow RGD, grey RCS, purple TLD, orange CSG, green CSF, and blue CCS

manufacturer was acquired for the SB tunnel, subsequently referred to as TBM #2. A similar soil conditioning program was used on both machines of the N125 project. The alignment of the NB and the SB tunnel run parallel with a short distance between the two tunnels. The TBMs, therefore, mine through nearly the same geology. The main difference between the two TBMs is the cutterhead and chamber geometry and their machine specifications (e.g., installed torque, rpm, etc.). The general view of these two TBMs is presented in Figure 4. Both TBMs are equipped with six earth pressure sensors on the bulkhead. However, the machines use different types of pressure sensors. The TBM #1 pressure sensors have a diameter of 140 mm while the TBM #2 uses two smaller size pressure sensors, 86 mm diameter and 30 mm diameter.

Figure 5 shows the location of the chamber pressure sensors of both TBMs. Two local apparent densities are calculated for each TBM. The top chamber apparent density ρ_T is calculated from the average pressure gradient between the two top pressure sensor levels, see Equation (6). The bottom chamber apparent density ρ_B is calculated from the average pressure gradient between the two bottom pressure sensor levels, see Equation (7).

Figure 4. The two EPB TBMs used on the U230 and N125 projects. TBM #1 (a) was used for both tunnels of the U230 project and is now used for the NB tunnel of the N125 project. TBM #2 (b) is used for the SB tunnel of the N125 project

Figure 5. Chamber pressure sensors on TBM #1 (a) and TBM #2 (b)

$$\rho_T = \frac{1}{2g} \left(\frac{p_2 - p_1}{z_T} + \frac{p_5 - p_6}{z_T} \right) = \frac{1}{2gz_T} (p_2 + p_5 - p_1 - p_6) \quad (6)$$

$$\rho_B = \frac{1}{2g} \left(\frac{p_3 - p_2}{z_B} + \frac{p_4 - p_5}{z_B} \right) = \frac{1}{2gz_B} (p_3 + p_4 - p_2 - p_5) \quad (7)$$

where g is the gravitational acceleration, p_1 through p_6 are the chamber pressures measured by the sensors in both TBMs, z_T is the vertical distance between the top two pressure levels, and z_B is the vertical distance between the bottom two pressure levels. In this analysis the left and right side gradients are averaged. The influence of adhesion between muck and metal surfaces on the apparent density distribution in the chamber is not considered for this analysis since the apparent densities are mainly analyzed after the mining process has stopped.

Figure 6 shows an example of the apparent densities in the bottom and top part of the chamber, ρ_B and ρ_T , the water density ρ_w , and the average of two pressure sensors in the top part of the chamber during and after excavation of N125 NB ring 1281. During the advance the apparent densities cycle with the rotation of the cutterhead. This cyclic behavior is due to the influence of asymmetric mixing bars attached to the back of the cutterhead. This influence ends when mining is stopped. The apparent density increases during the stop as expected due to consolidation, migration of foam bubbles into the surrounding ground, and possibly the end of the muck/chamber adhesion effect. The foam bubbles migrate into the ground in front of the face to reach an equilibrium with the lower pore water pressure of the ground. The pressure decreases as expected during the stop until it reaches ambient pressure or mining is presumed. Ambient pressure is the stable equilibrium pressure of the surrounding ground. The noise in apparent density data during the mining process is a result of other operational parameters like

Figure 6. Apparent densities of top and bottom chamber, ρ_T and ρ_B , water density ρ_w , and average pressure of the two top pressure sensors p_{16} of N125 NB ring 1281

torque, thrust, rotation speed, etc. Due to this noise the apparent density should mainly be interpreted during the stops. In this study, apparent density at the beginning of the stop has been used in order to eliminate the noise, the adhesion, the consolidation, and the foam migration effect as explained above.

5 Case Studies – U230 and N125 Projects

This section presents data from the U230 and N125 projects where the evaluation methods for apparent density described in section 3 were applied.

Figures 7a and 7c show the bottom and top chamber apparent densities of both the NB and SB tunnel of the U230 project and the virgin soil density from ring 0 to ring 755 estimated from data in the GBR (Soundtransit 2009). One apparent density value right after the end of mining is used for each ring. Figures 7b and 7d show the atmospheric foam injection ratio (FIR) and the bentonite injection ratio (BIR) for both tunnel drives. The soil types within the tunnel cross sections as well as waterhead and cover are shown in Figure 7e. Although, both tunnels are mined through similar geology and TBM #1 is used for the excavation of both tunnels, their apparent densities differ. The top chamber apparent density was below unity in both tunnels, but this was the case more often in the NB tunnel. This suggests that the NB tunnel had more issues with air pocket formation than the SB tunnel. The apparent density in the NB tunnel was in general lower than that of the SB tunnel despite the lower FIR values of NB. However, the bottom chamber apparent density reached values above the virgin soil density more often in NB than in SB suggesting more frequent plugging issues in NB. The improved apparent density values of SB are likely a result of the operator getting accustomed to the TBM and ground during the NB drive and applying the gained experiences during the excavation of the SB drive. In the area with decreasing and zero waterhead the top chamber apparent densities of both tunnels mainly remained below unity suggesting an air pocket was present in the chamber of both tunnels. The difference between top and bottom apparent density also increased in this area suggesting that the lack of water caused a less homogeneous mix in the chamber. In this area the BIR was increased for both NB and SB and the FIR was increased for NB. This in combination with the decrease in waterhead could have also lead to a general decrease in apparent density.

Figure 8 shows the bottom and top chamber apparent densities of both NB and SB tunnel of the N125 project and the virgin soil density from ring 0 to ring 1600. It also shows the ESUs in the tunnel cross-sections, cover, and waterhead. The bottom chamber apparent density of both tunnel drives was higher than the virgin soil density in several locations. However, the bottom chamber apparent density of the SB tunnel was higher than the virgin soil density essentially throughout the rings presented. The SB bottom chamber apparent density was more often above the virgin soil density and generally higher than that of NB. This suggests that the SB TBM had more plugging issues than the NB TBM. Although the top chamber apparent density was lower than unity in both tunnels, this was the case more often in the SB tunnel. This suggests that air pockets formed more often in the SB TBM than in the NB TBM. The SB top chamber apparent density was generally lower than that of NB. In the SB tunnel and specifically in the section of the alignment with low waterhead the plugging issues are fairly clear from the data. Two cutterhead interventions were necessary to resolve plugging issues in the SB TBM, one at ring 306 and

one at ring 571. The intervention at ring 306 was at the end of the first high apparent density peak, while the intervention at ring 571 was at the end of the second high apparent density peak. After the intervention at ring 571 the apparent density rose quickly again, which might be mainly due to the very low waterhead in that region. No cutterhead interventions were necessary for the NB TBM and all high apparent density issues were resolved by modifying the soil conditioning protocols.

Figure 7. Bottom chamber apparent density ρ_B , top chamber apparent density ρ_T , and virgin soil density ρ_s for NB (a) and SB (b) tunnels of the U230 project. Percentage of soil types inside tunnel cross-sections from ring 0 to ring 755 (c)

More specific cases of apparent density below unity and apparent density above virgin soil density will be discussed in Sections 5.1 and 5.2.

5.1 Apparent Density below Unity

During the excavation of ring 355 of the NB tunnel in U230 project, the TBM mined through an observation well that was not decommissioned before the project. Foam and pressurized air travelled

Figure 8. Bottom chamber apparent density ρ_B , top chamber apparent density ρ_T , and virgin soil density ρ_S for NB (a) and SB (b) tunnels of the N125 project. Percentage of ESUs inside tunnel cross-sections, cover, and waterhead at springline from ring 0 to ring 1600 (c)

Figure 9. Apparent densities of U230 NB ring 355 during which a blowout of a chamber air pocket occurred

through the observation well to the surface. This suggests that an air pocket was present in the chamber when the well was encountered by the TBM and as a result, pressurized air in the chamber found a path to the surface. The apparent densities and chamber pressures of ring 355 are shown in Figure 9. The top chamber apparent density was below unity at the beginning of the advance and decreased further during the first eight minutes, suggesting an increase in air pocket formation. The end of this decrease in apparent density ($t = 12:07$) appears to be the time when the observation well was hit. The apparent densities and pressures react as would be expected when an air pocket is released. The top chamber apparent density increases while the bottom chamber apparent density and top chamber pressure decreases. The bottom chamber apparent density decreases because the pressure in the top of the chamber decreases and the material in the bottom part of the chamber can expand towards the top. Both apparent densities increase quickly after mining is stopped which suggests that the air pocket continues to be released after mining is stopped.

Figure 10 shows the apparent density data for rings 111 and ring 157 of the N125 project's NB tunnel during which the air release valve on the bulkhead of the NB TBM was used to release the excessive air from the chamber. During ring 111, shown in Figure 10a, the apparent densities and pressure react as expected to the opening of the valve. The apparent density in the top part of the chamber was below unity when the valve was first opened. While the valve is open the top chamber apparent density starts to rise while the pressure and bottom chamber apparent density decrease. The valve is opened two more times until the top chamber apparent density is higher than unity. The pressure increases again after the valve is closed because excavated soil enters the excavation chamber replacing the released air pocket as a pressure medium. The data clearly indicates that an air pocket was present when the air valve was opened.

Figure 10b shows the data from ring 157 during which the valve was also opened. Compared to ring 111 this ring shows little to no reaction to the opening of the valve. The apparent density data is also very noisy and fluctuates largely around unity. During the second opening of the valve a slight increase in top chamber apparent density and decrease in pressure can be seen, but the apparent density starts to

fluctuate again after the valve is closed. The data indicates that no air pocket was present when the air valve was opened.

Figure 10. Apparent densities of N125 NB rings 111 and 157 during which the air release valve on the bulkhead was open (green shaded areas)

5.2 Apparent Density above Virgin Soil Density

Figure 11 shows the apparent density and operating parameter data for the U230 project's NB tunnel from ring 0 to ring 755. One apparent density value right after the end of mining was used for each ring. The thrust and torque values represent average values for each ring advance. The bottom chamber apparent density was higher than the virgin soil density in several locations. However, the area around ring 400 has the most rings with high apparent density. After the observation well blowout during ring 355 (see section 5.1) the foam injection was decreased to almost zero for the next two rings. Following this decrease in FIR, the bottom chamber apparent density, the thrust, and torque started to rise suggesting that a plug developed. The advance rate, however, increased at the same time and only decreased when thrust and torque decreased. Furthermore, the bottom chamber apparent density was not consistently above the virgin soil density in this area. Therefore, it cannot be assumed that a plug formed in the chamber. The bottom chamber apparent density also increased above the virgin soil

Figure 11. Areas of high apparent density, bottom chamber apparent density ρ_B , virgin soil density ρ_S , ambient pressure $p_{ambient}$, and advance rate v (a), thrust force F_T and Torque T (b), FIR, waterhead, cover, and soil types (c) for rings 0 to 755 of the U230 project's NB tunnel

density in a second area from right before ring 700 to the end of the tunnel drive. This increase is connected with controlled density fill (CDF) areas before and after a low cover highway undercrossing (13ft cover).

Figure 12 shows the data for the N125 project's SB tunnel between MLP and RVS, from ring 0 to ring 1600. Two interventions were necessary to resolve the plugging issues during this drive, the first intervention was performed at ring 306 and the second one at ring 571. Four areas can be identified where the bottom chamber apparent density is significantly higher than the virgin soil density (yellow shaded area in Figure 12). The first two areas are right before the two cutterhead interventions, the third is around ring 700 in CSG below the water table, and the fourth is around ring 1500 at the start of the TLD soil unit. In the first three areas of high apparent density, the operational parameters react as

Figure 12. Bottom chamber apparent density ρ_B , virgin soil density ρ_S , ambient pressure $p_{ambient}$, and advance rate v (a), thrust force F_T and Torque T (b), FIR, waterhead, cover, and ESUs (c) for rings 0 to 1600 of the N125 project's SB tunnel. Black vertical lines indicate the cutterhead interventions during ring 306 and ring 571. The yellow shaded area indicates areas with high apparent density

expected for plugging issues. The advance decreases significantly, torque and thrust increase, and the FIR is increased in an effort to increase the advance rate. Torque and thrust would also increase with an increasing advance rate, and high values are, therefore, only a sign for plugging issues when they occur along with low advance rates. The two cutterhead interventions confirmed that plugging occurred in the first two areas and the data suggests plugging also occurred in the third area of high apparent density. The decrease in apparent density and increase in advance rate right before the first intervention indicate that the increased FIR started to resolve the plugging issues. The plugging issues in the third area were resolved by increasing the FIR and using specialty, lubricating soil conditioners. No cutterhead intervention was necessary in this location.

6 Conclusions

The apparent densities can be used to assess the soil behavior in the excavation chamber of EPB TBMs. An apparent density below unity indicates the formation of an air pocket and can be a result of extensive use of foam and higher than necessary FER. An apparent density above the virgin soil density indicates the formation of a plug and results from less than necessary volume of soil conditioners or improper application of soil conditioners. In addition to the apparent density, operational parameters like pressure, advance rate, thrust, torque, and soil conditioning parameters have to be taken into account when assessing apparent density. The study performed on the N125 and U230 projects shows that the presented apparent density evaluations methods can be used to identify air pockets and plugging issues in the excavation chamber of an EPB TBM with a high degree of certainty.

Although the presented apparent density evaluation methods can help to identify air pockets and plugging issues some uncertainties remain. Further research should be performed to clarify the influence of lateral earth pressure coefficient and TBM operational parameters on apparent density. The authors intend to use data from future EPB TBM projects to continue and expand their analysis of apparent density. Further, the measurement of vertical pressure in the excavation chamber of an EPB TBM would allow for a better understanding of the coefficient of lateral earth pressure.

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Figure Captions

Figure 1. Air pocket relief valve as seen through the camera (left) and schematic of air relief valve (right)

Figure 2. Subsurface geology of the U230 tunnel alignment between CHS and PSST (Irish 2009). Soil Units are Fill (brown), Till and Till-like Soil (light pink), Till-like Soil (dark orange), Outwash (plum), Fluvial Sand (yellow), Lacustrine Sand (orange), Silt (light and dark turquoise), Clay (light and dark purple), Organic Material (green)

Figure 3. Subsurface geology of the N125 tunnel alignment from MLP (top right) to UWS (bottom left). ESUs shown are white ENF, yellow RGD, grey RCS, purple TLD, orange CSG, green CSF, and blue CCS.

Figure 4. The two EPB TBMs used on the U230 and N125 projects. TBM #1 (a) was used for both tunnels of the U230 project and is now used for the NB tunnel of the N125 project. TBM #2 (b) is used for the SB tunnel of the N125 project

Figure 5. Chamber pressure sensors on TBM #1 (a) and TBM #2 (b)

Figure 6. Apparent densities of top and bottom chamber, ρ_T and ρ_B , water density ρ_w , and average pressure of the two top pressure sensors p_{16} of N125 NB ring 1281

Figure 7. Bottom chamber apparent density ρ_B , top chamber apparent density ρ_T , and virgin soil density ρ_S for NB (a) and SB (b) tunnels of the U230 project. Percentage of soil types inside tunnel cross-sections from ring 0 to ring 755 (c)

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Figure 12. Bottom chamber apparent density ρ_B , virgin soil density ρ_S , ambient pressure $p_{ambient}$, and advance rate v (a), thrust force F_T and Torque T (b), FIR, waterhead, cover, and ESUs (c) for rings 0 to 1600 of the N125 project's SB tunnel. Black vertical lines indicate the cutterhead interventions during ring 306 and ring 571. The yellow shaded area indicates areas with high apparent density